

Implementing the FAIR Data Principles

What — How — Why

Implementing the FAIR Data Principles

What — How — Why

What do the FAIR principles stand for?

In order to ensure that scientific findings and the associated data can be found, used, verified and reused by humans and machines, the data should meet certain basic data quality requirements. The FAIR principles help to implement these quality standards and increase the value of data.

Findable

To ensure that data can be referenced and remains findable in the future, a persistent identifier is assigned to it. Additionally, the machine-readable metadata stored together with the data helps to increase the findability of the data on the web.

Accessible

The data is accessible via a standardized internet protocol. If necessary, this protocol can also include authentication and authorization processes. The metadata remains freely accessible, even if the data itself is not — or is no longer — accessible.

Interoperable

To ensure that (meta)data is compatible with different computer systems and software, it should be machine-readable and written in accessible language that complies with the standards of the research community. Persistent identifiers can be used to link data to publications, individuals, and to other data.

Reusable

Thorough data documentation supports the clarity of the data and its future use. Open file formats also contribute to reusability. Finally, adding a license to the data clearly specifies the conditions under which the data may be legally reused.

Why make your data FAIR?

Machine-readable and comprehensive metadata, the publication of the data in a FAIR-compatible repository and the licensing of the data all help to ensure that the data can be found more easily on the web and can be used and cited by others. This in turn increases the reproducibility and thus the robustness of one's research and builds confidence in the research results.

A FAIR-compatible repository should:

- allow the selection of a license,
- assign persistent identifiers, and
- allow the entry of machine-readable metadata via a structured metadata form as well as the possibility to upload separate data documentation files.

Making your data FAIR is also important for your own research: Good data documentation helps you to understand the data even years later, to trace its creation processes and to be able to reuse the data yourself.

What does the Swiss National Science Foundation require?

The Swiss National Science Foundation expects its grantees to publish their data in publicly accessible digital repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles. At the same time, FAIR data does not mean that the data is accessible without any restrictions. The SNSF supports its grantees with a list of FAIR-compatible repositories and a checklist to identify such repositories.

- List of FAIR repositories: <https://www.snf.ch/en/WtezJ6qxuTRnSYgF/topic/open-research-data-which-data-repositories-can-be-used>
- Checklist to identify FAIR repositories: https://www.snf.ch/media/de/zKRJknEq0OHE5pEQ/Checklist_data_repositories.pdf

Inform yourself

University Library Zurich

The website of the Open Science Services informs about FAIR and Open Data.

Website: <https://www.ub.uzh.ch/en/wissenschaftlich-arbeiten/mit-daten-arbeiten/FAIR-und-Open-Data>

Literature

Wilkinson et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3, 160 018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Publishing information

© March 2026
University of Zurich

Editor

University Library Zürich
Open Science Services

Editorial office

Melanie Röthlisberger, Laetitia Kaiser, Samuel Nussbaum, Stefanie Strebel

Version

Version 1.1

Contact

University of Zurich
Open Science Services
Pfingstweidstrasse 60b
8005 Zürich
Switzerland
www.ub.uzh.ch